

Towards a National Low Traffic Neighbourhood Dataset

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GISRUK 2024

Summary

Low traffic neighbourhoods (LTNs) form a major part of active travel infrastructure planning within the UK. However, despite considerable academic and public discourse, there remains a lack of empirical studies on these neighbourhood zones. This study looks to create the foundations for a national dataset of plausible low traffic neighbourhoods. Neighbourhoods are defined by identifying the bounding features of each zone. LTNs are indicated through the presence of modal filters and high internal neighbourhood accessibility. Modal filters within neighbourhoods are extracted through analysis of OpenStreetMap data. Internal accessibility is assessed through comparison of shortest-path lengths of pedestrians and motor vehicles.

KEYWORDS: Low Traffic Neighbourhoods, Accessibility, Active Travel, OpenStreetMap

1 Introduction

Within the UK, transportation is the largest greenhouse gas emitter by sector (Department for Transport, 2022b). To address the climate crisis, alternatives to motorized transport have received increased prominence, discourse and funding (Lamb et al., 2021). Active travel offers low-carbon alternatives for short travel distances, whilst at a reduced cost and beneficial to public health (Chapman et al., 2018; Aldred et al., 2018).

However, active travel remains underutilised in the UK (Lovelace et al., 2017; Aldred and Goodman, 2020; Claudy and Peterson, 2014), with underdeveloped networks compared to those of motorized transport (Wardlaw, 2014). Investing in walking and cycling networks is shown to increase participation, emphasizing the need for strategic investment (Dill, 2009; Marques et al., 2015; Hull and O’Holleran, 2014).

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In 2022, the Department for Transport announced the Cycling and Walking Investment Strategy (CWIS) to outline its approach to funding of active travel infrastructure (Department for Transport, 2022a). A priority of the report is to make existing streets more ‘people friendly’, placing greater emphasis on pedestrian and cycling accessibility on roads usually dominated by motor vehicles. This is currently being attempted through methods such as Low Traffic Neighbourhood (LTN) schemes.

The concept and implementation of LTNs originates in the 1970s (Transport for London, 2020), however has seen increased discourse recently. This is largely due to rapid implementation of LTN schemes during the COVID-19 pandemic, which provided a unique trial opportunity (Gustafsson, 2022; Buehler and Pucher, 2023; Aldred et al., 2021).

Several studies have been done on the impacts and equity of LTN zones (Goodman et al., 2020; Aldred et al., 2021; Goodman et al., 2023). However, a large gap in research literature exists. Only 4 empirical studies on LTNs have been done outside of London, UK (Pearce et al., 2021; Parkes et al., 2022; Boveldt et al., 2023; Nutall and Lucas-Smith, 2020). To research LTNs rigorously, studies must occur across a greater sample of discrete spatial locations. Particularly as the nature of transport systems in London is not replicated to the same depth elsewhere in the UK currently.

A potential cause of this research gap relates to a lack of available datasets. As of writing, there is no consolidated dataset of plausible LTN zones. The closest attempts have looked to calculate street-level traffic values, however do not consider neighbourhoods as cohesive structures (Nutall and Lucas-Smith, 2020). Through the creation of a plausible, open and national LTN dataset, researchers will be enabled to fill existing gaps within literature.

2 Research aims and objectives

Based on the identified research gaps and challenges, the following aim has been formulated:

- *Create a national dataset of LTN boundaries*

Four research objectives are set out to guide the creation of this dataset:

- **Objective 1:** Define spatial boundaries for neighbourhoods
- **Objective 2:** Identify modal filters within neighbourhoods
- **Objective 3:** Compare the internal neighbourhood accessibility via active and motorised travel modes
- **Objective 4:** Classify appropriate neighbourhoods as plausibly low traffic zones

3 Methods, data, and software

3.1 Data and software

This project uses an open-source stack of data and software. All data in this project is accessed from OpenStreetMap (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2017), aside from OS Open Roads from Ordnance Survey, which is also open-access for academic and public use. The completeness of OpenStreetMap is far from perfect, and some open datasets provide richer detail and accuracy (Tait et al., 2022; Hong et al., 2020). However, unlike these other datasets, it does provide national level coverage at a high level of detail (Ferster et al., 2020). All analysis is undertaken using a geospatial Python stack (Boeing, 2017; Hagberg et al., 2008; Jordahl et al., 2020). All code relating to this project can be found on Github (<https://github.com/Froguin99/LTN-Detection>).

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Neighbourhood boundary definition

To create a dataset of LTNs, a delineation of all neighbourhoods is first required. Whilst fundamentally there is no universal definition for a neighbourhood, this study considers neighbourhoods purely in the context of transport (Yan and Dennett, 2023). Specifically, we work from the perspective of the most vulnerable street users (walkers and cyclists). We define a list of bounding features that constrain a neighbourhood by where a person can travel comfortably (Table 1).

Bounding Feature	Feature Type	Data Type	Source	Justification
Railways	All above ground rail transport, not including trams	Polyline	OpenStreetMap	Railways have been shown to act as dividers for neighbourhoods (Mitchell and Lee, 2014)
Bus routes	Roads where a bus route is shared by greater than 2 bus services	Polyline	OpenStreetMap and NAPTAN	Busy bus routes have shown to create higher stress levels for active modes, particularly when cyclists must share space with them (Teixeira et al., 2020).
Roads	Roads with a classification of A or B, or roads with a function of motorway, major road, minor road, trunk road or primary route	Polyline	Ordnance Survey Open Roads	Neighbourhoods are comprised of the lowest tiers of road hierarchy
Landuse type	Landuse with OpenStreetMap tags of industrial, railway, brownfield, commercial, farmland, meadow, wood, scrub, water, golf course, track or park	Polygon	OpenStreetMap	Neighbourhoods are generally considered to be residential or city centre areas.
Rivers	All rivers, not including culverts or tunnels	Polyline	OpenStreetMap	Rivers are a natural boundary between locations

Table 1: Neighbourhood Boundary Feature Datasets

With bounding features accessed, 5 meter buffers are created down centre-lines of any polyline. The study area boundary is then erased by the center-line buffers and landuse polygons to create multiple neighbourhoods zones (Figure 1). These areas are cleaned by removing neighbourhoods with no roads, fewer than 2 junctions or an area less than 5000m². This ensures small areas such as the centres of roundabouts are not included as neighbourhoods.

Figure 1: Boundary processing

3.2.2 Modal Filter Identification

Modal filters are the predominant method which LTNs area are created. They allow permeability for active modes whilst acting as barriers to private motor vehicles, ensuring trips with origins and destinations external to the neighbourhood do not shortcut through. Modal filters take various forms (Figure 2). Streets in this section of analysis are sourced from OpenStreetMap rather than Ordnance Survey to ensure pedestrian streets are represented.

Barrier filters refer to physical objects such as planters or bollards which are used to disrupt car traffic (Figure 2 - Top right). Barriers with tags "bollard", "bus_trap", "entrance", "planter", "sump_buster" or "wedge" are accessed for the study area. Only barriers which intersect streets are kept for analysis. Any barriers part of linestrings are split into their constituent parts. If any of these barriers intersect a street, only one barrier from the original linestring is kept to avoid over-counting.

Bus-gates prevent private motor vehicles from using a road, whilst allowing all other traffic through (Figure 2 - Top left). Streets with bus-gates are likely quieter in terms of overall traffic than roads without. Street segments with bus-gates are tagged for later analysis.

Cycle contra-flows provide bi-directional travel for cyclist, but single directions for cars (Figure 2 - Bottom right). Streets where this is present are tagged for future analysis.

Street continuations refer to streets where the mode type changes (Figure 2 - Bottom left). We

Figure 2: Examples of modal filters. From top left to bottom right; barrier filters, bus-gate filter, cycle contra-flow filter, street continuation filter

extract segment of streets where the mode has changed from motorised to an active mode, whilst the road name has remained the same. All filters are spatially joined to their respective neighbourhoods for analysis.

3.2.3 Internal neighbourhood accessibility

Whilst the presence of modal filters in and around a neighbourhood indicates interventions to reduce traffic, a measurement of the permeability of a neighbourhood provides a different perspective on how plausible the zone is to be low-traffic. By measuring the internal accessibility of each neighbourhood, we look to find zones where walking and cycling have greater advantage over motor vehicles by travel distance. A more accessible neighbourhood is assumed to foster other benefits such as increased safety and sense of community, which are not measured in this study.

For a given study area, the street networks for both driving and walking are accessed from OpenStreetMap. Nodes which are common to both networks are henceforth used as origins and destina-

tions for the analysis. For each neighbourhood these common nodes are accessed, including those on boundary roads to the neighbourhood. The length of shortest paths from all common nodes in the neighbourhood are measured to all other nodes in the neighbourhood for both the driving network and walking network. These distances are stored per neighbourhood.

3.2.4 Neighbourhood Classification

With metrics calculated for accessibility and the presence of modal filters, the expected relationship between both measures will be investigated through Pearson's correlation coefficient. Neighbourhoods with high presence of filters and high pedestrian to motor accessibility ratio are expected to align with LTN zones. A threshold value for both measures will be set to allow for classification of neighbourhoods into either plausibly low traffic or not. From there, this methodology is to be applied to the whole UK to create a national dataset, allowing further research.

4 Preliminary results

All results at this stage are preliminary and will be subject to future revisions.

4.1 Neighbourhood boundary definition

An example of the neighbourhood areas can be seen in Figure 3. Neighbourhoods are most commonly bounded by roads or green-space. Some artificating can be seen due to use of landuse types within the boundaries. This is particularly prevalent when narrow woods or parks are present.

Figure 3: Neighbourhood delineation in North Leeds, UK

4.2 Modal Filters

Modal filter detection Figure 4 shows the distribution of modal filters throughout Newcastle Upon Tyne. Note that no bus-gates are found within neighbourhoods in this study area. The neighbourhoods found to have a greater number of filters align with the location of LTN schemes in the city. These can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Modal Filters Per Neighbourhoods in Newcastle Upon Tyne

4.3 Internal neighbourhood accessibility

Internal accessibility is found to always be at least equal between walking and driving. The mean difference of shortest path lengths across the neighbourhood is used to assess the accessibility difference. In Newcastle Upon Tyne, walking is on average 139 meters shorter than driving, with a maximum distance of 1156 meters. Visualisation of this is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Internal Neighbourhood accessibility in Newcastle Upon Tyne

5 Conclusion

This research has attempted to provide the foundations of methods for the creation of a national LTN dataset. Initial results provided plausible neighbourhood definitions, along with two methods of assessing how likely a location is to be considered "low-traffic". Four types of modal filters have been identified and located for the study area. Internal accessibility has also been calculated for every neighbourhood within the study area showing accessibility differences ranging from 0m to 1156m.

6 Acknowledgements

This work is made possible by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) of Great Britain (grand number EP/S023577/1).

7 Biography

Chris Larkin is a PhD student at the EPSRC Centre for Doctoral Training (CDT) in Geospatial Systems at Newcastle University, researching active travel.

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